

AI/ML-Assisted Connected & Autonomous Vehicles for 6G and Beyond

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Consumer
Experiences.
**Automotive
Grade.**

About me

RAVI PUVVALA
VP of STRATEGIC PARTNERSHIPS, HARMAN

Ravi Puvvala is leading Cybersecurity innovation at Harman, leveraging an ecosystem of partners that includes 5G technology suppliers, edge cloud partners, security startups around the world.

Prior to Harman, he was the founder & CEO of Savari. In this role, he led his company's Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) core technologies to be adopted by various Automotive OEMs, smart cities/states around the world. Savari was acquired by Harman in Feb 2021.

He is a frequent speaker on the topics of 5G, V2X, cybersecurity at various standards organizations, consortiums, mobility conferences. He serves as an advisor to various startups, transportation institutes, government bodies.

Ravi has 30 years of experience in the Automotive and Telecommunication industry. He has worked for various startups and fortune 100 companies in the Silicon Valley during his career.

Ravi holds BS and MS degrees in Computer Science from Bangalore University, India and Arizona State University, United States.

An Automotive Powerhouse

- Deep automotive expertise in hardware and software
- Rigorous testing of our solutions
- Technology that powers 50 million cars globally

**A FORCE LIKE
NO OTHER**

SAMSUNG

- Global top five brand
- Significant R&D with a strong patent portfolio
- World leader in semiconductor production

6G Next Wave

Pervasive Infrastructure

Increasing city intelligence and unlocking smarter, safer communication between **Unmanned AV**, **Connected AV** and the environment.

- Improve traffic management (flow & efficiency) in congested areas via processing of **perception-based sensors (1 TB of data per hour)** to provide real time data for end-users.
- Extended reality (XR) interactive gaming, 100 hours of Netflix content in one second
- Improve vehicle and pedestrian safety via the combination of **edge AI, C-V2X** and **high precision localization technologies** and solutions.

Traffic Management

Use case #1

Leverage 6G network with MEC to provide safety alerts for users over Uu

Leverage existing smartphone platforms to improve safety

Leverage standards compliant V2X messages

Collision prediction logic provides alerts to users

VRU - Collision Course Awareness

Use case #2

Leverage 6G network with MEC to provide safety alerts for users over Uu

Leverage existing smartphone platforms to improve safety

Leverage standards compliant V2X messages

Collision prediction logic provides alerts to users

Vehicle to Edge to Vehicle

Vehicles integrates various inputs to provide high value outputs to the Augmented, Extended Reality Displays

Empowering, Immersive, Co-Pilot

Empowering

Eyes Forward,
Mind Focused

Promoting Calm &
Dispelling Anxiety

Unobstructed View

Immersive

Relevant POI Display

Concierge

Enhanced
Directional Audio

Co-Pilot

AI Driving Assist

Sight Beyond Sight

Fast Response Time

In Cabin Experiences (ICX)

AR HUD

AR/XR Heads Up Display

- XR Windshield
- Large Field of View

Software Defined Framework

Object detection

- AI / ML-powered system delivers right image at the right time
- Computer vision and ML deliver real-time 3D Object detection with low latency
- AR-UX orchestration for contextualized POI recommendations and monetization

Sensors / Audio

Sight beyond sight

- Sight-Beyond-Sight
- Directional Audio alerts for faster emergency response
- 6-DoF multi-sensor data fusion for accurate positioning

AI/ML for Secure In Cabin Experience

AI helps in making connected autonomous vehicles safer, smarter, greener

Use Case	Hosted	Description	AI/ML Model
AI/ML for improving situational awareness	Vehicle, Edge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Analyze vehicle network traffic and detect targets, collision avoidance algorithms in real-time 	Supervised Learning – Classification
AI/ML for predictive maintenance	Vehicle, Edge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Analyze unlabeled raw data (various logs, sensor data, etc.) and detect anomalies 	Unsupervised Learning – Clustering
AI/ML for autonomous driving	Vehicle, Edge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rules are ineffective or broken due to data variations and condition changes AI/ML models can be trained to replace the brittle, fragile rules for every changing security environment 	Supervised Learning – Classification
AI/ML for security	Vehicle Edge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Analyze data from various sources and provide real-time threat detection and remediation 	Supervised, Unsupervised, NLP
AI/ML for governance	Cloud	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ML models can be used to automate the processes of compliance, continuous penetration testing, vulnerability management 	Reinforcement Learning

Thank You

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